

TEN YEARS AFTER — A History of Library Technicians in NSW

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ABSTRACT

The author reviews the effective self-help programme carried out by library technicians in New South Wales throughout the 1970s. He shows how a relatively small group of para-professional workers was able to mobilise its own and outside resources in achieving industrial and organisational recognition. The contribution of the State library is defined and acknowledged. In conclusion, library technicians in a wide range of libraries are urged to complete 'the integration of library technicians into the library workforce'.

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The origin of library technician courses in Australia has been the topic of some discussion recently within the Library Association of Australia. Jean Hagger (*Aust Lib J*, November 1982) traced the decisive role of the Victorian Branch of the Association in the establishment of Australia's first library technician course, in Melbourne, in 1970. It is sufficient to state here that the Victorian Branch's interest in para-professional training dated from the mid-sixties. The NSW TAFE Library Practice Certificate Course commenced in 1973; it has now been replaced by the Library Technician Certificate Course and the last graduate of the LPCC emerged in 1982.

Ten years after the introduction of a library technician course in NSW it is fitting to review the progress of its graduates. Two organisations, the Library Technicians' Branch of the NSW Public Service Association (PSA) and the LAA's Library Technician Section NSW Group, have played a central role in the development of library technicians in NSW. In NSW the Sheldon Award¹ of 1973 created Library Officer positions for which there were various types of requirements.

In a letter to the *Library Technician Newsletter*², Warren Horton, a central participant in the negotiation of the Sheldon Award, noted that the 'Library Officer' positions were established with the intention that they be occupied eventually only by staff who had completed or who were undertaking library technician training. However the qualifications of the staff employed at the date that the Sheldon Award took effect meant that some temporary equations were made by the Public Service Board for other non-technician qualifications. Before the Sheldon Award, Librarians, Archivists and Library Assistants had belonged to the same branch of the PSA. Thereafter Librarians and Archivists remained in the Professional Division of the PSA and Library Officers moved to the General Division and formed their own branch.

The LAA's Library Technician Section — NSW Group had its beginnings in July 1975 when the third year part-time students of the Library Practice Certificate Course decided that they wanted to know what was happening about the status of the course and what sort of jobs they would be able to obtain. This group called themselves the Committee for the Advancement of Library Officers (CALO) and held their first general meeting in August 1975. The Group held a number of meetings, corresponded with and visited employers, unions, government departments and also consulted the Library Association of Australia. This resulted in it becoming a Special Interest Group of the LAA and it changed its name to the Advancement of Library Officers Special Interest Group, becoming part of the NSW Branch and being funded by the LAA in 1976.

The Group changed its name yet again in March 1977 and became the Para-Professional

Special Interest Group. This was to prevent ambiguity between the terms 'Library Officer' and 'Library Technician' until a national definition was obtained.

1977 marked the first formal contact with technicians in other states, although there had been some informal contact with the Victorian technicians after the 1976 Workshop on the Education of Library Technicians. Correspondence with the Queensland technicians began and a regular interchange of newsletters was undertaken.

In response to a request from the LAA for the Group's views on library technician membership the Group requested a special category of membership: 'a) To give library technicians a separate identity within the Association. b) To provide an incentive for library technicians to join the LAA.'³ In 1978 the Group made a major effort to achieve portability of qualifications by lobbying TAFE for the Library Practice Certificate Course to be submitted to the LAA Board of Education for recognition. This took two years to achieve, recognition being finally granted at the end of 1979.

Two major events took place in 1979. The second National Workshop on Library Technicians was held in Sydney in May, and a Library Technician Section of the LAA was formed. The Workshop concentrated on the education of library technicians and on issues such as the industrial status and the role of the LAA and the Board of Education in the promotion and recognition of library technicians. Sub-groups of state and national, special, school, tertiary and public librarians examined the LAA's policies on library technicians including the lists of tasks expected to be performed by library technicians and made recommendations based on experience or expectations in these libraries.

The Workshop also provided library technicians from all states with a chance to meet and discuss issues of common concern. The NSW, Queensland and South Australian technicians all agreed that a Library Technician Section of the LAA was desirable. The other major state, Victoria, disagreed. A formal meeting of library technicians was held after the Workshop and this established a National Steering Committee on Library Technicians (NSCOLT) as a compromise.

Two weeks later the formation of a Library Technician Section of the LAA was approved at a meeting of the Association's General Council in Adelaide. The Section was formed in response to approaches from the special interest groups of South Australia, Queensland and NSW. These felt that there was a growing need for improved national communication and understanding on library technicians and called for the section to be formed to help develop this within the LAA. The NSW Group was instrumental in the foundation of the Section. This was reflected in NSW technicians occupying the positions of Vice-President (Anne Brinson) and Treasurer (Ian Gordon) on the Executive of the new Section. By 1979 the Group had developed strong ties with the PSA Library Officers Branch (as the Library Technicians Branch was then called). A valuable exchange of opinion and advice took place, as well as individuals serving on the committees of both organisations.

The mood of the LAA at the time was expressed by the then President, John Brudenall.⁴

The involvement of technicians in the LAA is important. Our Association must become the national organisation for all library and information workers and our objects should be relevant to technicians and others. We are all concerned with improving library and information services and in the standards of work and calibre of people employed in libraries.

The Department of TAFE's Library Practice Certificate Course Review Committee had undertaken a major study for the purpose of reviewing the course and published its findings in 1979.⁵ A number of recommendations were made including the following:

1. The Library Practice Certificate Course be re-organised and the syllabus rewritten to incorporate:
 - (a) a task oriented approach based on tasks identified as those performed by library technicians and taking into account those tasks likely to be performed in areas such as library display and publicity, audio-visual equipment and materials, services for children and supervision of non-professional staff.

- (b) concurrent work experience.
 - (c) general electives from which students select and complete two or more.
 - (d) library oriented electives from which students select and complete at least two.
2. The Library Practice Certificate Course have the following minimum admission requirements:
- 1. School Certificate (NSW) with attainment of Level 3 or better in English, or equivalent qualifications.
 - ...
 - 9. The revised course have a new title, Library Technician Certificate Course, to distinguish it from the present course.

The revised course was introduced in 1980. The NSW Library Technician Section Group, through a series of articles by Anne Brinson in the *NSW Library Technician Newsletter*, began a campaign under the slogan 'Technicians for Technician Jobs'.

The Group was concerned at the increasingly common practice of professionally qualified librarians filling jobs at the library technician level due to the contraction in the professional sphere. Anne Brinson argued that sound management policy required the structuring of library jobs to take advantage of the practical skills of library technicians. The advantage would be a better balance in staff structures.

In the same year attempts were made to extend the activities of the Group to Newcastle with two members of the committee speaking at a meeting of technicians in that city. In 1981 further attempts were made to involve country technicians in the Group's activities when meetings were held in Wollongong and Newcastle.

1980 saw the first technician members of the LAA's NSW Branch Council — one as a sectional councillor and the other as an elected Branch Councillor. Since that time there have always been at least two technicians on NSW Branch Council. The Group was by this stage holding functions with other sections of the LAA, including a meeting with the Special Librarians' Group and a workshop with the Children's Section.

The First National Library Technician Conference was held in Adelaide in July 1980. It was a great success as it provided technicians from across Australia with the opportunity to come together and discuss problems of mutual concern. The confidence of technicians in their ability to solve problems was strengthened by the fact that the conference had been organised by library technicians for library technicians.

Following the conference the Section planned a year of consolidation of state groups. This placed a considerable burden on the NSW Group as the National Executive was centred in Sydney in 1981. This period saw some groups prosper and others decline. One real success was that of the ACT Library Technician Sectional Group in planning and holding a major seminar on children's libraries. This function helped the ACT group establish itself and it has not looked back since.

A noticeable shift took place in the editorial line of the *NSW Library Technician Newsletter* in 1981 as well. It was now assumed that libraries employed technicians and this led to a greater questioning of library structures. Articles began to develop the theme that the emergence of library technicians, coupled with the new technologies being used in libraries had resulted in changes in the staff structures. There were now two levels of trained staff — the professional (librarian) and the para-professional (library technician). The role of the librarian had become more specialised, and in the special library the librarian was now likely to have subject qualifications in addition.

This led to the emergence of the technicians as a second tier in the library staff structure. The technician role now comprised the routine work involved in the daily running of a library, and the providing of back up services in inter-library loans, routine reference work, pre-programmed data base searches, copy cataloguing, accessioning placing and the following up of book orders. The nature of this role was beginning to be recognised in policies and

awards governing the employment of library technicians. The contribution of the State Library of NSW in this was acknowledged in the March 1981 issue of the *NSW Library Technician Newsletter*.⁶

It should be said that much of the credit for the development of the understanding and employment of library technicians in NSW lies with the State Library. The State Library of NSW had a long record of support for library technicians.

This identification with the State Library of NSW and its management policies was inevitable; it was the first major employer, in NSW, to recognise the potential of the library technicians and it was State Library staff who were instrumental in the negotiations which led to the Sheldon Award. By 1981 the committees of the PSA's Library Technician Branch and the LAA's NSW Library Technician Sectional Group were almost interchangeable, a situation which was strengthened in 1982 and continues today. The Branch has developed into a group of library technicians capable of determining their own role in the library structure and seeking appropriate gradings and remuneration. Technicians employed under NSW awards and agreements enjoy some of the best conditions and salaries for library technicians in Australia. In September 1981 a new agreement between the PSA and the PSB was signed which allowed for: (i) The change of terminology from Library Officer to Library Technician. (ii) The introduction of a Senior Library Technician position. This change was partially brought about by the phasing-out of the Library Practice Certificate and the introduction of the new Library Technician Certificate. Whilst both are library technician courses the LPC had an HSC minimum entry level and was a four-stage course and the LTC has a School Certificate entry level and is a three-stage course. Discussing the new agreement at a union meeting the Vice President of the Library Technician Branch (who had acted as the negotiator) noted that the 'atmosphere of acceptance of library technicians in the library scene provided by the work of the LAA and in particular its Library Technician Section had greatly aided the Union's case'.⁷ This statement sums up the attitude of library technician activities in NSW. The LAA provides the 'atmosphere of acceptance' and then technicians in other organisations, usually unions, follow this up with activities to formalise technician status. In 1982 the *NSW Library Technician Newsletter* was dominated by the ramifications of the new PSA/PSB agreement. Job design emerged as the catch-cry.

The introduction of Senior Library Technician positions had increased the career opportunities of library technicians. At the same time it had highlighted the need for a complete review of library positions in the NSW Public Service. Although many para-professional positions had undergone some reform over the years there had been no general evaluation of the employment of library technicians and the attendant changes in both professional and para-professional work. It was hoped that with the establishment of the Senior Library Technician position and the establishment of the library technician classification at universities, attention would be given to job design for library technicians. The creation of the grading of Senior Library Technician reinforces the notion of career orientation. Previously, the career prospects for para-professional staff were virtually non-existent unless they were prepared to undertake a degree and obtain professional qualifications.

The need for a restructuring of positions within the State Library, TAFE Library Service and Government Department Libraries is now the most important issue facing library technicians in NSW. Despite major reviews by the managements of the State Library and TAFE Division of Library Services progress towards a formal restructure has been slow. Obstacles along the way have included the Public Service Board, staff ceilings, the drought, a wage pause and a Departmental Secretary who had no love for library workers.

This struggle to achieve a formal restructure of library positions in the NSW Public Service brought library technicians to grips with the problem of defining levels of performance for library technicians. The Committee of the PSA's Library Technician Branch developed a set of definitions which were published in the September 1982 issue of the *NSW Library Technician Newsletter*.

Since that time these definitions, which are fundamentally a development of LAA

guidelines, have gained a degree of acceptance amongst employers, educators and library technicians themselves. Library technicians employed in public libraries are mainly covered by the Municipal Employees' Union. An award exists in this area but no library technicians are actively involved in the MEU at the time of writing. Recently an award has been handed down for library technicians in university libraries. It remains to be seen how this will be implemented. Hopefully consultation will take place with those library technicians already employed by the universities.

The future for library technicians in NSW holds promise. If library technicians in Public Libraries, Special Libraries and University Libraries can emulate the success of the PSA's Library Technician Branch, then the integration of library technicians into the library workforce will be almost complete.

In the current economic climate demarcation problems between librarians and library technicians will no doubt arise. If managements review staff structures and design jobs around qualifications, professional or para-professional, and reach agreement with employee groups then these problems may be avoided.

Many who become library technicians do so to avoid the responsibilities and pressures of a professional. They are thus reluctant to get involved with unions and professional associations. When they do it often leads them out of the library technician area; of the ten people on the Executive of the Library Technicians Branch of the PSA, in 1982 five were undertaking further studies (mostly in librarianship or with the intention of becoming librarians) and another two have done so in 1983. This may hold implications for the future; para-professional positions may well revert to being a training ground for some professionals as well as providing a career path for library technicians. This could result in undergraduate courses in librarianship placing an emphasis on library technician training as a pre-requisite for entry and structuring courses around an assumed para-professional knowledge.

Library technicians are sure to play a larger role in libraries in the forthcoming years.

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